

**2nd International Conference on
Healthcare and Allied Sciences**
Focal Theme : Transformation towards Sustainable Healthcare
ABSTRACTS & PROGRAMME

Date : 26th and 27th September 2018

Venue :

Grand Blue Wave Hotel, Shah Alam, Malaysia

Organized by:

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10	<p>The Influence of Giving Honey on The Score Decreasing of Pain as The Result of Intravenous Blood Taking Action on Child at The Emergency Department of Hospital Cirebon City</p> <p>Ayu Yuliani S <i>Tasikmalaya Health Polytechnic, Ministry of Health, Indonesia</i></p> <p>Yeni Rustina; Nur Agustini <i>University of Indonesia, Ministry of Health, Indonesia</i></p>
11	<p>The Influence of Assertive Training on The Assessment of Self-Assertiveness of Early Adolescent Female Victims of Bullying in Junior High School 52 Bandung</p> <p>Desi Sundari Utami <i>Prodi D III Keperawatan Poltekes TNI AU Ciumbuleuit Bandung, Indonesia</i></p> <p>Suryani <i>Fakultas Keperawatan Unpad Bandung Indonesia, Indonesia</i></p> <p>Nunung Nurjanah <i>Prodi S2 Keperawatan Stikes Jendral Achmad Yani Cimahi Bandung, Indonesia</i></p>
12	<p>Employee knowledge relations and the role of the supervisor against Unsafe Behavior in Company K3 in PT. Pindo Deli Pulp & Paper Mills II Karawang</p> <p>Eldawati <i>Stikes Kharisma College, West Java Indonesia, Indonesia</i></p>
13	<p>The Relationship Response Time of Acute Coronary Syndrome (ACS) and Status Alteration of Heart Rhythm at ACS Patiens In Emergency Department at Tk II Dr Soepraoen Malang Hospital</p> <p>Rahmania Ambarika; Novita Ana Anggraini <i>Health Science Institute of Surya Mitra Husada Kediri, East Java, Indonesia</i></p>
13:00-14:00	<p>Lunch</p> <p>Venue : Royale Songket</p>
14:00-15:30	<p>Session III : Open paper Session: Sustainable Healthcare</p> <p>Venue : Dewan Rebana I</p> <p>Chairman : Dr. Madhumitha Sen</p> <p>Co-chairman: Mr. Ramesh Prasath Rai</p>
1	<p>The Relationship of Attitude, Subjective Norms and Perceive Behavior Control and Implementation The Spiritual Needs of Patient by The Nurse in Intensive Care Unit, Dr. Dradjat Prawiranegara Hospital, Serang</p> <p>Asra</p>

The Relationship of Attitude, Subjective Norms and Perceive Behavior Control and Implementation The Spiritual Needs of Patient by The Nurse in Intensive Care Unit, Dr. Dradjat Prawiranegara Hospital, Serang

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ABSTRACT

Patient in critical condition not only needs biological nursing care service, but also they are requisite spiritual support from health care provider and family. Until now, nursing that focus on intensive care unit is still limited related to spirituality aspect, and there are many factors associated to the nurse's behavior in implementation of spiritual nursing intervention. Theory of planned behavior explained the intention and someone's behaviors is influenced by attitude, subjective norms, and perceive behavior control. This study aimed to investigate the relationship and dominant effect of attitude, subjective norms and perceive behavior control and implementation the spiritual needs of patient by the nurse in intensive care unit, dr. Dradjat Prawiranegara Hospital, Serang.

The design of this study used was descriptive correlation with cross sectional study approach. Data was collected by using questionnaires with likert scale. Respondents of this study were nurses in intensive care unit with the total number 30 nurses. Data was analyzed by using Pearson's product moment and multiple linear regression.

The result showed that the attitude, subjective norm and perceive behavior control were simultaneously significantly relationship to nurse's behavior in fulfilling the spiritual needs of patient in intensive care unit of dr. Dradjat Prawiranegara hospital, Serang that is 79.8% (p value 0,001), and perceive behavior control was the most dominant factor with relative contribution 45.24% (proportion 36.1% of 79.8%) if compare to attitude 28.45% and subjective norm 26.31%.

This study recommends that the increasing of competence of nurse in supporting the spiritual needs is important by using modification of behavior from perceive behavior control determination through training continuously, therefore nurse rise their self-control and self-confident upon behavioral appearance.

Key Words: *Spiritual care, Theory of planned behavioral (TPB), Intensive care unit*